

Artikel yang berjudul: Addressing the Challenges of Using Artificial Intelligence in Learning Through a Project-Based Learning Approach menggunakan artikel review yang terdapat pada referensi-referensi. Rereferensi berikut bersumber dari jurnal-jurnal international yang berkaitan dengan Pembelajaran yang berbasis pada Project-Based Learning

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